

c/o Mr. Abass Hadjian,
Personal Assistant to the Governor General,
The Ostandari,
Bandar Abbas,
IRAN.
28 October 1970.

F. S. Burgess, Esq.,
Awards Branch,
Department of Education and Science,
Elizabeth House,
39, York Road,
London. S.E. 1.
ENGLAND.

Your Reference: UP 67/1751.

Dear Mr. Burgess,

I enclose my accounts for travel expenses incurred in the process of research for last year. I must apologize for the considerable delay in sending you these accounts. The problem has been that I am rarely in Teheran when Mr. Stronach, the Director of The British Institute of Persian Studies, is there, since my supervisor, Mr. R. Pinder-Wilson cannot, of course, from England be expected to vouch for the accuracy of these research expenses.

I assume that the grant is taken as having expired on October 1st, so that I have not included on this account a major trip begun on that day.

My continuing work in Iran from October 1st, is being financed by The Wainwright Fund for Near Eastern Archaeology of The University of Oxford, who have given me a block sum for the purpose. Much of this, as you can imagine, has been spent on the payment of this large backlog of uncollected expenses. I am also supported, though not financially, by The British Institute of Persian Studies.

I would be grateful if you could tell me if it is correct form to submit any report or other information to the Department on the work I have carried out under your aegis. I would like to thank you for your helpfulness in administering the Department of Education and Science three year grant, which has provided the financial backbone of my rather unusual and expensive work.

Yours sincerely,

Andrew Williamson